

BALANCING EFFICIENCY AND FAIRNESS: AI IN INTERNATIONAL DISPUTE RESOLUTION

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the multifaceted role of artificial intelligence (AI) in the context of international commercial arbitration. It discusses how AI is being integrated at various procedural by both parties and arbitral institutions. The author examines the benefits of AI, such as cost reduction, increased efficiency, and enhanced legal analysis, as well as its challenges, including concerns over transparency ("black box" issues), bias, and legal legitimacy of AI-assisted decisions. Emphasis is placed on the need for ethical frameworks, transparency standards, and human oversight to ensure that technological advancement does not compromise due process or parties' trust in arbitration.

Nowadays, AI is increasingly being introduced into various fields of activity. The legal industry, including arbitration, is no exception to this trend. AI is computer systems capable of performing tasks that require "human" thinking (recognizing speech, processing natural language, learning from data)¹. In other words, AI represents the ability of computer systems to perform tasks that require human intelligence: information analysis, learning from experience, decision making. Modern AI systems, especially those based on machine learning and neural networks, are capable of processing huge amounts of data, identifying complex relationships and making predictions with high speed and accuracy. In the legal field, AI is already used for such tasks as: automated translation of documents, intelligent search in databases of legislation and decisions, analysis of contracts for risks and typical errors, forecasting dispute outcomes based on precedents and even generating draft legal acts based on specified parameters. Today, in the arbitration process, AI can act as an auxiliary tool at different stages. Parties to commercial disputes are using AI tools at various stages of the proceedings, and arbitrators and lawyers are using algorithms for document analysis, enforcement, and case management. This is part of the overall digital transformation, with the

¹ Odongo, R. (2021). AI (AI) in International Arbitration. Nairobi Center for International Arbitration. <https://ncia.or.ke/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/ARTIFICIAL-INTELLIGENCE-AI-IN-INTERNATIONAL-ARBITRATION.pdf>

introduction of electronic claim portals, ODR systems, and smart contracts². For example, in India, the Supreme Court has formally allowed arbitration agreements to be concluded by email and amended the Arbitration Act to allow “electronic means” for the formation of such agreements. These changes highlight that AI and digital technologies are already penetrating the commercial arbitration sphere, promising to improve the efficiency of procedures and expand access to jurisdiction. This trend certainly has a number of advantages. Firstly, AI significantly speeds up routine processes and reduce costs. Automation of repetitive operations such as document sorting and analysis, case management, and translation of texts makes it possible to process large volumes of information without tedious manual work. Research has shown that the use of AI for legal research and document review can reduce the time required to complete tasks from months and years to seconds³. Machine learning already enables specialized programs to process and structure large amounts of information in seconds, select relevant materials, and even generate drafts of procedural documents. This significantly reduces the workload of arbitrators and representatives of the parties, allowing them to focus on developing a legal position and strategic aspects of the case. In essence, such AI tools perform the tasks of a “junior lawyer,” while acting with greater speed and accuracy. As a result, dispute resolution is significantly accelerated: algorithms are able to generate draft decisions faster than a person can do manually. This reduces the accumulation of cases, reduces arbitration costs for the parties, and makes the procedure more affordable⁴. AI has already been integrated into leading commercial legal platforms such as Westlaw and LexisNexis, and its use is increasingly recommended for widespread use in arbitration practice in order to improve efficiency and reduce costs. In addition, AI contributes to a deeper and more accurate legal analysis. Modern algorithms are able to process complex, multi-layered data, identifying relationships and patterns that might otherwise go unnoticed by humans. For example, intelligent systems effectively identify key arguments contained in the parties’ documents and automatically find relevant or previously missed legal precedents. Using machine learning, programs learn from thousands of previous decisions and can predict the outcome of disputes, which helps parties build the right strategy, since predicting the outcome allows them to adjust their position and arguments at an early stage. Finding relevant legal norms, doctrine, and precedents is a labor-intensive part of preparing for a case. Platforms with AI tools can speed up this process: for example, Jus Mundi has launched Jus - AI, an assistant that answers questions based on a vast database of arbitration decisions and documents. Lexis+AI and Westlaw Edge, legal information products, integrate GPT models to understand a lawyer’s natural language query and return accurate results with sources. They also provide analytics: for example, Westlaw Edge can analyze the practice of a specific judge or arbitrator on request, showing the inclinations in decisions. For arbitration, where it is often necessary to study foreign laws and precedents, such tools are especially useful. Of

² Comprés , T. (2025, May 6). Global Miami magazine. Global Miami Magazine - a Hub for Miami's Booming International Business Community. <https://globalmiamimagazine.com/2025/05/06/the-role-of-technology-in-international-arbitration/>

³Odongo, R. (2021). AI (AI) in International Arbitration. Nairobi Center for International Arbitration. <https://ncia.or.ke/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/ARTIFICIAL-INTELLIGENCE-AI-IN-INTERNATIONAL-ARBITRATION.pdf>

⁴Bhumika Indulia . (2025, January 8). Arbitration in the Era of AI: What the Future Holds. SCC Times. <https://www.sconline.com/blog/post/2025/01/08/arbitration-in-the-era-of-ai-experts-corner/>

course, AI cannot yet completely replace a legal researcher – it is not trusted without verification – but in routine queries it saves a lot of time.

Reducing time costs with the help of AI can also be seen in the process of selecting an arbitrator. By analyzing a large volume of biographical data and rulings, AI tools can help select candidates with the necessary qualifications, while taking into account their possible biases. Here, it is not exactly AI that comes to the fore, but rather databases and analytics. For example, the Arbitrator Intelligence project collects feedback and information on the behavior of arbitrators in different cases to help parties make informed decisions⁵. The platform does not provide a ready-made answer, but systematizes the information: how many cases the arbitrator has handled, the tendency to grant motions for evidence, the average duration of trials under his or her chairmanship, etc. In the future, AI may be able to recommend arbitrators for a specific dispute profile, taking into account their experience, and also predict how a particular candidate may treat certain arguments. However, it is necessary to take into account that such systems are created in compliance with confidentiality: information about arbitrators should not contain references to specific cases. This is an example of how AI tools can increase the transparency of the arbitration services market by reducing dependence on a limited number of renowned arbitrators and giving a chance to new professionals. However, it is important to note that excessive automation of selection can lead to a decrease in individual assessment and unintentional discrimination. In this regard, AI in this case should be used as an auxiliary tool, and the final decision should remain with the parties or the relevant appointing authority. Nevertheless, even in this form, modern technologies significantly increase transparency and accountability in the procedure for the formation of the arbitral tribunal, strengthening trust in arbitration as a dispute resolution mechanism.

Another advantage of using AI in international arbitration, which is important for the parties to the dispute, may be predicting the outcome of the case. Thus, the most complex and intellectually rich form of using AI in arbitration is predicting the outcome of a dispute or, at least, assessing the probability of success of a particular position. For example, ArbiLex is aimed at arbitration: it analyzes uploaded legal documents: claims, responses to claims, contracts, decisions on similar cases – and, based on embedded machine learning algorithms, produces a probabilistic forecast of how the case may be resolved⁶. This is especially valuable for the parties at the preparation stage: based on the forecast, they can decide whether to continue the dispute, whether to conclude a settlement agreement and on what terms. Another platform, Case Crunch, was initially used to predict banking disputes in the UK, but the technology can be expanded. Of course, no such system guarantees 100% accuracy – the arbitral tribunal may decide otherwise – but the high success rate demonstrates that AI systems can detect patterns that are invisible to humans. The risk, however, is that such predictions may introduce some bias: for example, if an arbitrator learns that “the machine thinks the claimant is 90% likely to win,” this may subconsciously influence their decision. Therefore, such tools are usually used only by parties for internal risk assessment or by

⁵Arbitrator Intelligence | About. Arbitratorintelligence.vercel.app . <https://arbitratorintelligence.vercel.app/about>

⁶Abdurakhmanova, N. (2024). LEGAL REGULATION OF THE USE OF AI IN ONLINE ARBITRATION: INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL ASPECTS. *Izhtimoiy-humanitarian fan larning dolzarb muammolari / Actual problems of social and humanitarian sciences / Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 4(8). <https://doi.org/10.47390/spr1342v4i8y2024n47>

arbitral institutions for statistical analysis, but not by the arbitrators themselves when making an award.

Noting the use of modern technologies in international arbitration, it is worth emphasizing that AI can be used not only by the parties, but also by arbitrators. AI-based tools facilitate the process of formulating a decision, helping to build its logical structure. Generative models can turn an arbitrator's sketches and notes into a coherent text, which is then, if necessary, corrected by a person. The DLA Piper study notes that generative AI is already being used to create "essays" – for example, converting transcripts or notes into draft statements - and editing such drafts is much faster than writing from scratch⁷. The arbitrators themselves note that AI-based tools simplify the process of writing a decision and eliminate the need for countless checks, allowing them to concentrate on the substantive part. In other words, the system has become a kind of multifunctional proofreader that automatically checks the integrity of the text, style and correctness of references, while a person formulates the final conclusions and justifications. As a result, the structure of the arbitration act becomes more logical, since even complex arguments are initially formulated in a clear sequence, and the arbitrator only refines the nuances. This approach reduces the risk of missing key points and ensures the integrity of the arbitration decision, which is certainly an advantage of using modern technologies.

Despite a number of advantages of using AI in international arbitration, this phenomenon still carries certain risks, considering which, first of all, it is necessary to mention the issue of the legitimacy of the arbitration award when using AI. Thus, the widespread use of AI may lead to new arguments when challenging arbitration awards. For example, a party may apply to the court with a statement that the dispute was actually resolved not by a person, but by a program, which means that the procedure for forming the arbitration panel prescribed by law was not followed. Such a situation may be a consequence of the lack of empathy and human understanding in AI. Complex commercial conflicts often involve emotional and human aspects. Arbitrators often use a comprehensive assessment based on experience, a sense of justice, and sometimes even empathy for the bona fide party. AI, on the other hand, lacks a real understanding of human values. Research notes the importance of emotional intelligence and direct human interaction in dispute resolution, which is inaccessible to AI⁸. In other words, an AI-based tool may make a "cold" decision, which reflects another potential problem – the risk of machine bias. This drawback is associated not only with the development of the technology in a particular state, but also directly with the machine learning process. For example, if in the past arbitrators systematically made decisions against a certain category of companies, the AI may consider that belonging to this category is a factor for losing, and "advise" the corresponding decision. In addition, speaking about a certain "bias", it is also worth noting the risks of politically biased decisions made by AI. Thus, due to interstate relations, AI may make a decision against an "unfriendly" jurisdiction. Such situations, in turn, may become grounds for the cancellation of the arbitration award. Although there are no such precedents to date, it is worth noting that

⁷IA Meets AI – Rise of the Machines | DLA Piper. (2023). DLA Piper. <https://www.dlapiper.com/en/insights/publications/arbitration-matters/2023/ia-meets-ai-rise-of-the-machines>

⁸Arbitration Tech Toolbox: AI as an Arbitrator: Overcoming the "Black Box" Challenge? - Kluwer Arbitration Blog. (2024, August 23). Kluwer Arbitration Blog. <https://arbitrationblog.kluwerarbitration.com/2024/08/23/arbitration-tech-toolbox-ai-as-an-arbitrator-overcoming-the-black-box-challenge/>

if the arbitrator made a decision following the conclusion of an analytical program based on AI, the dissatisfied party will try to use this situation to cancel the decision.

One of the key shortcomings of AI today is the “black box” problem. “Black boxes” are AI systems whose internal mechanisms remain a mystery to their users⁹. In other words, there is no transparency in the operation of the algorithms: the user can only see the input data and the result of their consideration, while the process of arriving at a certain conclusion, i.e. what factors were taken into account by the algorithm when making a decision, remains undisclosed. Many modern AI systems, especially deep neural networks, operate according to complex non-linear models that are difficult to explain in understandable terms. In the context of arbitration, this can be seen as a serious obstacle: the arbitration decision must be motivated, therefore, the arbitration panel must understand the reasons for the interim decisions they make. If it is unclear why the AI recommended rejecting a particular piece of evidence, such advice cannot be relied upon. Moreover, the lack of transparency undermines trust: even if the algorithm is statistically correct 95% of the time, the party that loses because of the “AI advice” will always doubt whether there is an error in the remaining 5%¹⁰. In this regard, arbitrators avoid using “black” algorithms where justification is required.

Confidentiality issues are of no small importance in arbitration. In this context, another problem may arise: for example, if a party uploaded case materials to an external AI service for translation or analysis, the other party may be outraged that its confidential data was actually transferred to a third party - a software developer, which, in turn, is a violation of the confidentiality agreement. In addition, ethical aspects such as liability for the leakage of confidential data have not yet been studied. Thus, the question still remains open: who is responsible for the dissemination of data, for an incorrect decision due to the bias of the AI system: the arbitration panel or the developers of the AI software? These legal aspects are still outside traditional regulation and create an area of uncertainty.

The use of AI in international arbitration promises significant benefits: reduced transaction costs, improved quality of legal analysis, automation of routine tasks, acceleration of procedures, etc. At the same time, as rightly noted in the Chartered Institute of Arbitrators Guide to the Use of AI in Arbitration (2025), with each new level of automation new ethical challenges appear that cannot be ignored without compromising the legitimacy of the arbitration institution itself¹¹. AI is a system capable of performing intellectual tasks that require human participation: text analysis, information processing, prediction of consequences, etc. In legal practice, AI means are used to search for and analyze precedents, draft documents, assess risks, predict case outcomes, and, more recently, in arbitration proceedings. Systems such as ROSS Intelligence, LexisNexis, Kira Systems are currently actively used in law firms and arbitration institutions to automate various stages of legal analysis. However, despite a number of advantages, the current level of development of AI, especially language models, is far from perfect. Generative models are notorious for their tendency to invent convincing-sounding but false information if they have gaps in their

⁹Kosinski, M. (2024, October 29). What is black box AI (AI)? IBM. <https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/black-box-ai>

¹⁰Arbitration Tech Toolbox: AI as an Arbitrator: Overcoming the “Black Box” Challenge? - Kluwer Arbitration Blog. (2024, August 23). Kluwer Arbitration Blog. <https://arbitrationblog.kluwerarbitration.com/2024/08/23/arbitration-tech-toolbox-ai-as-an-arbitrator-overcoming-the-black-box-challenge/>

¹¹Chartered Institute of Arbitrators (CI Arb), *Guideline on the Use of AI in Arbitration* , https://www.ciarb.org/media/m5dl3pha/ciarb-guideline-on-the-use-of-ai-in-arbitration-2025-final_march-2025.pdf

knowledge. This makes them potentially unreliable sources for decision-making, especially in cases that require strict adherence to the rule of law, accurate interpretation of legal concepts, and consideration of the unique context of the dispute. Moreover, even if AI is able to formally formulate a reasoned decision, the problem of the lack of genuine legal judgment and professional responsibility remains. Arbitration, unlike an automated procedure, presupposes not only the technical application of the rule, but also consideration of fairness, good faith, balance of interests of the parties, and other categories that require human assessment. Thus, the successful use of AI requires the development of international standards and an ethical framework governing its use, as well as ensuring a sufficient level of human oversight and participation. Developments in technology open up new horizons for arbitration, but these opportunities cannot be considered without appropriate regulatory and institutional support. Therefore, the task of the international legal community is not simply to introduce AI into arbitration, but to do so thoughtfully, taking into account all legal, ethical and procedural consequences

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